

SETTLING OF GLASS WOVEN FABRIC IN STEEL RTM MOULD: IMPACT ON RESIDUAL STRESSES?

J.M. Balvers, H.E.N. Bersee, A. Beukers
Delft University of Technology, Faculty of Aerospace Engineering,
Design and Production of Composite Structures,
Kluyverweg 1, 2629HS Delft, The Netherlands
Corresponding author's E-mail address: J.M.Balvers@TUDelft.nl

SUMMARY

With embedded fibre Bragg grating sensors it is proven that thermal loading of steel RTM mould containing glass woven fabrics leads to different behaviour when fabric still has to settle. Heating and cooling along the same trajectory do not imply a reversible process with respect to expansion/contraction of the preform.

Keywords: Residual stresses, fibre Bragg grating sensors, RTM processing, oil heated/cooled steel moulds

INTRODUCTION

Embedded optic sensors with fibre Bragg gratings (FBGs) are increasingly applied for studying the manufacturing process of advanced composites (i.e., products made of a combination of fibrous reinforcement and a resin system). The advantages of being less intrusive because of the small physical size and the multiplexing ability give the engineers the opportunity to add a nervous system to their products. Furthermore, this network of sensors can also be of use for structural health monitoring during the product's operational lifetime. In this study, the focus is on monitoring a process belonging to the group of liquid composite moulding (LCM): resin transfer moulding (RTM). A step-by-step approach was adopted to investigate the influence of each individual process step (i.e., mould closing, injection, curing, and demoulding) on the Bragg response. In Part I of this proceeding an observation during earlier experiments is discussed. In here, it will be shown that subjecting the mould to thermal cycles led to different expansion/contraction behaviour of the dry woven fabric. The fabric had to settle and therefore behaved differently in the first heating path. In analogy with prestressed concrete, in which the weakness of concrete in tension is overcome by prestressing tendons, it is thought that different initial conditions (prior to injection and curing) of the woven fabric can lead to differences in residual strain afterwards. In Part II a novel method is introduced to characterise the residual strain as a function of temperature. The FBG technology is applied to measure the strain in annealed specimens. During annealing the glass transition point is passed and constraints between fibres and resin are released. The drop in stiffness of the resin is used for setting up a locus for zero stress in the woven fabric. The results are discussed and conclusions are drawn with respect to settling of glass woven fabric in a steel mould and the impact on residual stresses. But as a starting point, the theory behind FBGs is briefly outlined.

THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

Briefly explained, a Bragg grating in an optical fibre, which is illuminated by a broadband spectrum light, reflects a narrow-band optical signal, satisfying the Bragg condition, at a particular wavelength (i.e., the Bragg wavelength, λ_B), whereas all other wavelengths of the broadband spectrum light are transmitted.

The Bragg wavelength is defined as the centre wavelength of the reflected narrow-band optical signal and is a function of the effective refractive index, n_{eff} , and the grating period, Λ . That is,

$$\lambda = 2n_{eff}\Lambda \quad (1)$$

According to this expression, a shift in the Bragg wavelength is observed when either the effective refractive index or the grating period is changed. Thus, strain and thermal effects that modify the physical or geometric properties of the grating are monitored by looking at the shift in the Bragg wavelength [1].

In terms of axial strain ε and temperature T , the shift of the Bragg wavelength is determined by differentiating the above equation with respect to these two parameters. Without giving the complete derivation, the expression becomes:

$$\frac{\Delta\lambda_B}{\lambda_B} = (1 - P)\Delta\varepsilon + (\alpha_n + \alpha_f)\Delta T \quad (2)$$

where P is a so-called effective photo-elastic coefficient, and α_n and α_f are the thermo-optic and thermal expansion coefficients of the optical fibre, respectively.

However, when an FBG sensor is bonded to or embedded in a host structure, thermally induced axial stress may be developed due to a mismatch between the coefficients of thermal expansion (CTE) of the optical fibre and host structure [2]. The above equation should then be modified to:

$$\frac{\Delta\lambda_B}{\lambda_B} = (1 - P)[\Delta\varepsilon + (\alpha_H - \alpha_f)\Delta T] + (\alpha_n + \alpha_f)\Delta T \quad (3)$$

where α_H is the host's coefficient of thermal expansion.

PART I: OBSERVATION

During earlier experiments the influence of each individual process step of RTM on the Bragg response was monitored. An additional step between mould closing and injection of the standard RTM process was to subject the dry preform to several thermal cycles. Below a brief description is given of the materials, type of optical fibre, equipment, and the procedure. Results of the experiments are summarised in tables.

Material and sensors

The preform consisted of ten layers [0°/90°] of an 8HS satin weave glass fabric (TenCate, The Netherlands) and had a size of 290mm x 290mm. The thickness of the

compressed preform was 2mm and resulted in a fibre volume fraction of about 57%. Between the fifth and sixth layer two types of sensors were embedded: an optical fibre with three FBGs and a K-type thermocouple. Both sensors were fixated with an instant glue (E1100 Scotch-Weld™ 3M). Schematically, their positions are illustrated in the left part of Figure 1. The optical fibre was aligned to one of the principal directions of the fabric.

The optical fibres used for these embedding experiments were so-called Draw Tower fibre Bragg gratings (DTG[®]s) and were supplied by FOS&S, Belgium. The core and cladding diameter had a diameter of 6 and 125µm, respectively. Furthermore, an organic modified ceramic coating protected the optical fibre and resulted in an outer diameter of 195µm. On arrival, the optical fibres were given a heat treatment for stabilisation.

For the experiments described in this proceeding FBGs with either 4mm or 8mm grating length were used. In the analyses, constant values were assumed for the coefficients. That is, the values for (1-P), α_n , and α_f are 0.78, $5.9 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ K}^{-1}$, and $0.55 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ K}^{-1}$, respectively.

Equipment

The RTM mould, consisting of two matched mould parts, was made of steel and had a mould cavity of 300mm x 300mm x 2mm. Both the upper and lower mould part had an integrated oil circuit. Oil heating was performed by a Tool-Temp 380 oil heater, which was connected to a standard desktop PC by a DAQ unit. An in-house developed software tool allowed control of the mould temperature.

The inlet (I) and vent (V) are illustrated in the left part of Figure 1. Since the preform was smaller than the mould cavity, a runner was created such that the injection started at the periphery and continued inwards to the vent.

The optical fibre was connected to an FBG interrogator, supplied by FOS&S, and the peak wavelengths and spectrum were monitored using a standard desktop PC and a software tool developed by FOS&S. The K-type thermocouple was connected to a Keithley DAQ unit and another standard desktop PC.

Procedure

In Figure 1 the procedure is schematically shown. When the experimental set-up was ready and sensors were connected, the preform was subjected to a thermal cycle, in which temperature was varied between room temperature and 90°C.

Figure 1: Determination of the slope

Both temperature and wavelength shift were simultaneously recorded. In total three preforms were tested according to the same strategy but with slightly different thermal cycles.

Initial results

In the experiments described above it was assumed that there was no longitudinal strain ($\Delta\varepsilon = 0$) present in the optical fibre. This means that Eq. 3 reduced to:

$$\Delta\lambda_B = [(1 - P)(\alpha_H - \alpha_f) + (\alpha_n + \alpha_f)]\lambda_B\Delta T = a_{\text{emb,exp}}\Delta T \quad (4)$$

Plotting the change in wavelength, $\Delta\lambda_B$, versus the difference in temperature, ΔT , revealed a linear relation between these two parameters. An overall parameter, $a_{\text{emb,exp}}$, which is the slope of this experimentally measured relation of an embedded optical fibre, was used to characterise each individual heating and cooling path in the thermal cycle. Although it was possible to calculate the host's CTE, this was not directly of interest for this study.

In Table 1 an overview is given of the calculated slopes of each heating and cooling path for one of the experiments. The mean value of the slope was based on the output of the three FBGs. All slopes fluctuated between 0.0222 and 0.0241 nm/°C, when H1 was left out of consideration. The first heating path showed a smaller slope (66% of the mean of all other slopes).

This difference in slopes between the first heating path and the rest of the thermal cycle was also observed in the two other experiments indicating probably that the fabric had to settle. Table 2 shows the difference between the slope of the first heating path and the average slope for the rest of the thermal cycle.

Table 1: Overview of slopes for one of the experiments (Experiment No. 1)

Period	H1	C1	H2	C2	H3	C3	H4	C4
Temperature path [°C]	RT - 90	90 - 50	50 - 90	90 - 50	50 - 90	90 - RT	RT - 70	70 - RT
Slope [nm/°C]								
Mean	0.0154	0.0239	0.0226	0.0237	0.0230	0.0241	0.0222	0.0238
Standard Deviation	0.000165	0.000365	0.000196	0.000391	0.000155	0.000459	0.000410	(*)

H is heating, C is cooling, RT is room temperature, H4 and C4 correspond to the cure cycle

(*) No standard deviation because mean is based on single value

Table 2: Difference between first heating path and the rest of the thermal cycle

Experiment No.	Slope H1	Average slope rest of thermal cycle	Percent difference
	[nm/°C]	[nm/°C]	[%]
1	0.0154	0.0234	34.19
2	0.0170	0.0237	28.30
3	0.0150	0.0236	36.38

When a value of $12 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ K}^{-1}$ was assumed for the CTE of steel and the Bragg wavelength was set to 1550nm and these were subsequently substituted into Eq. 4 together with the already given values for the other coefficients, a theoretical slope of 0.0238nm/°C was found. Thus, except for the first heating path, the optical fibres reacted as if they were embedded in steel (see Table 2).

In the first heating path the preform seemed to be less affected by the expansion of the steel mould and thus the slope was lower. Does this mean that the initial stress state in the fibres can be differed by letting the preform undergo a thermal cycle prior to injection? If yes, then a difference would also occur in the residual stress state.

PART II: VERIFICATION

To verify whether thermal loading of a dry preform affected the residual stress state, two plates were manufactured. This time, each laminate consisted of ten layers (290mm x 290mm, [0°/90°]) of a similar 8HS satin weave glass fabric but from another supplier. The supplier was changed to Hexcel, France, because a specific sizing was needed in order to be compatible with the bi-component RTM 6 resin system, which was also supplied by Hexcel.

The bi-component RTM 6 resin system is similar to its monocomponent equivalent and has the following manufacturer's recommended cure cycle (MRCC): preheat the resin to 80°C, preheat the mould to 120°C, inject the resin and cure at 160°C for 75 minutes followed by a postcure of 120 minutes at 180°C.

The RTM 6 resin system is frequently used in the aerospace industry and was chosen because of its curing at an elevated temperature. Due to the MRCC, the dry preform had to be heated to 120°C and therefore this combination of resin system and fabric was ideally for testing the effect of thermal loading.

The two panels were manufactured using the RTM process and with the equipment as described in the previous section. All process parameters were kept the same. That is, stacking sequence, mould closing procedure, the flow-rate and maximum pressure level,

Figure 2: Cure cycle of RTM 6

the purging time, and the cure cycle (Figure 2). Furthermore, the same cleaning and mould preparation procedure was followed. The only difference in the process that was intentionally created was the thermal loading, to which one of the dry preforms (090401) was subjected. The thermal loading consisted of two times the cure cycle, which is shown in Figure 2, and was performed after the mould was closed but before the actual injection.

For the moment, it was assumed that based on the outcome of the previous experiments there was no need for embedding optical fibres. Even though the fabric was supplied by another company, the type of fabric was still the same and therefore similar behaviour should be observed. This assumption will be validated later on as part of the future work.

Basis of technique

Recently, a novel method to measure residual stresses in unidirectional glass fibre reinforced plastics has been published by two researchers of the University of the Witwatersrand, South Africa [3]. It relied on the releasing of constraints between unidirectional fibres and resin through an annealing process. While steadily heating up the specimens, residual strains were released and when the resin reached its glass transition point, its modulus decreased to negligible values. Above the glass transition temperature, the composite behaved as the reinforcement because of the loss of stiffness of the matrix. This change in behaviour was used for creating a so-called locus of zero stress in the reinforcement. The difference between this locus and the measured strain gave an indication of the mechanical strain in the reinforcement. The method depended solely on the elasticity of the reinforcement for determination of internal stresses. Using Hooke's law and the volume fractions, the residual stresses at room temperature were easily obtained.

Although the basis of the technique has been adopted, the experimental method was slightly different. In this study, a mechanically clamped optical fibre with FBGs measured the Bragg response for specimens that were slowly heated up in an oven.

Specimens

A Unitom cut-off machine of Struers was used to cut several specimens of 135mm x 15mm. From each plate nine specimens were obtained, which were all oriented in the same direction. Furthermore, for mechanical clamping four strips were cut of the same material for each specimen. These strips had dimensions of 35mm x 10mm. Figure 3 showed schematically an assembled specimen. A K-type thermocouple, which is not shown in the figure, is taped on the specimen and near the measurement section of approx. 70mm.

Figure 3: Assembly of specimen

Procedure

After assembling a pair of specimens (i.e., one of each plate), the specimens were hung in the middle of an oven (type VTU 60/60 of the German company Vötsch Industrietechnik GMBH). To illustrate this, one has to rotate Figure 2 counter clockwise for 90° and clamp it at the top part of the specimen. The cables of the optical fibre and thermocouple were fed through the oven. Both cables were connected to their designated PCs (see earlier section). Both data readings were simultaneously started and shortly after this the program of the oven. In thirteen hours the temperature was steadily increased from 20°C to a maximum temperature of 250°C . A slow heating rate of 17.7°C/hr was preferred in order to avoid a thermal lag. Cooling was not of interest and therefore the fastest cooling rate was chosen. As soon as the program was finished data recording was stopped and data saved for post-processing.

Results

To verify the experimental method a first trial was done with an aluminium specimen in order to ensure proper clamping of the optical fibre to the specimen. Chemical bonding was not an option because the glue can have a negative influence on the Bragg response and also the optical fibre will be lost after each test. Due to cost motivation, reusability of the optical fibre was preferred. Moreover, simply taping the optical fibre to the specimen resulted in fibre slippage and other disturbances in the Bragg response due to mismatch in CTEs of the tape and specimen. The only suitable method found so far is mechanical bonding using strips and small bolts. Both the specimen and strips were made of aluminium 51ST such that both had the same CTE. In Figure 4a the thermal strain inside the aluminium specimen is plotted as a function of temperature. The slope is $24 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ K}^{-1}$ and equals the theoretical CTE of aluminium 51ST [4]. The curve was obtained by solving Eq. 3 for $\alpha_H \Delta T$.

When the same post-processing steps are taken for a composite specimen, the curve of Figure 4b is obtained. Clearly visible is the transition point at around 220°C . Below this

Figure 4: (a) Validation of method with reference material (Aluminium 51ST),
(b) Locus of no stress in glass woven fabric

temperature, which was in fact the glass transition temperature, the specimen behaved as a composite and above as the reinforcement only. In this case, the reinforcement consisted of ten layers of glass woven fabric. To determine the locus of zero stress a first order polynomial was fit through the data points between 230°C and 250°C. Extrapolating this line to zero and looking at the difference between the locus and the experimental data, one can say the following: the specimen had a negative residual strain at room temperature and this was steadily released when the glass transition point was approached. Just before the glass transition point, the residual strain had a positive overshoot.

For each tested specimen the locus of zero stress was individually determined. The slopes are listed in Table 3. Clearly visible is the identical behaviour above the glass transition point. On average the slope is $7.686 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ K}^{-1}$ and $7.490 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ K}^{-1}$ for plates 090401 and 090403, respectively. This slope represents the thermal expansion coefficient of the glass woven fabric. Specimen VII of plate 090403 may be regarded as an outlier (see Table 3) and, unfortunately, the optic fibre attached to specimen VII of plate 090401 failed during testing and thus data recording was not completed for this specimen.

Subtracting the experimental data from the locus of zero stress resulted in the plots of Figure 5.

Figure 5: Residual strain in woven glass fabric – (a) without thermal loading (090403), (b) with thermal loading (090401)

Table 3: Slope of 'Locus of zero stress'-line (10^{-6} K^{-1})

Plate	Specimen number							Mean	Standard deviation
	II	III	IV	V	VII	VIII	IX		
090401	7.679	7.503	7.907	7.799	7.474	-	7.754	7.686	0.144
090403	7.412	7.811	7.31	7.768	6.599	7.688	7.844	7.490	0.384

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

Whether thermal loading has an influence on residual strain can now be answered when looking at Figure 5 and Table 3. Although on average the residual strain curves for each panel coincided, less spread in experimental data was observed for the panel that had undergone thermal loading. Since none of the other process parameters or inputs were intentionally altered, it may be concluded that thermal loading did not change the residual strain curve significantly, but resulted in less spread in experimental data between the specimens mutually. This could also have influences on the scatter in mechanical properties. However, after analysing the specimens that were annealed, it turned out that some of the optical fibres were not perfectly aligned with the fibres of the reinforcement. A maximum angle of 2° was measured for one of the specimens. This small misalignment can also be the cause of the spread in experimental data. If the spread was due to the misalignment, one can conclude that the observation of settling and the approach of thermal loading did not influence the residual strain.

FUTURE WORK

It should be noted that, although up to seven specimens were tested for each plate, only one plate for each case was considered: one for the traditional RTM process and the other one for an RTM process that included a thermal loading step. More plates need to be analysed to establish a solid conclusion.

The effect of having a small misalignment needs also to be investigated. It is therefore proposed to analyse specimens having different fabric orientations.

Furthermore, the experimental method will also be applied to specimens that are not fully cured in order to follow the strain build-up when the cure temperature is changed.

Lastly, the assumption of constant values in Eq. 3 needs to be validated for the applied temperature range. Measurements on a bare optical fibre should be done to find the baseline.

References

1. Antonucci V., Giordano M., Cusano A., Nasser J., Nicolais L., "Real time monitoring of cure and gelification of a thermoset matrix," *Composites Science and Technology*, Vol. 66, No. 16, 2006, pp. 3273-3280.
2. Kuang K.S.C., Cantwell W.J., "Use of conventional optical fibers and fiber Bragg gratings for damage detection in advanced composite structures: a review," *Applied Mechanics Review*, Vol. 56, No. 5, 2003, pp. 493-513.
3. Reid R.G., Paskaramoorthy R., "A novel method to measure residual stresses in unidirectional GFRP," *Composite Structures*, Vol. 88, No. 3, 2009, pp. 388-393.
4. Aalco [website], April 2009, URL: <http://www.aalco.co.uk>